

PROJECT T SATTRA

Product summary

THE PRODUCT?

An Innovative desktop application for small and medium healthcare facilities.

With focus on efficiency, efficacy, and excellence in healthcare management

WHO ARE OUR

Its Everyone!

STAKEHOLDERS?

What is it built with?

Following the OpenSource model, it utilizes the Flutter framework along with PostgreSQL to achieve the goals of management

Key Values

- ✦ Flutter Framework
- ✦ Dart Language
- ✦ Supabase / PostgreSQL

Distinct user roles and Fluent UI design cater to intuitive usage.

Modules cover Patient Management, Medicine Tracking, Appointment Scheduling, and Report Generation, ensuring comprehensive healthcare management.

```
7 class MyApp extends StatelessWidget {
8   // This widget is the root of your application.
9   @override
10  Widget build(BuildContext context) {
11    return MaterialApp(
12      title: 'Flutter Demo',
13      theme: ThemeData(),
14      // This is the theme of your application.
15      //
16      // Try running your application with "flutter run". You'll see the
17      // application has a blue toolbar. Then, without quitting the app,
18      // change the primarySwatch below to colors.green and then running
19      // "flutter reload" (press "r" in the console) will update the app.
20      // Or simply save your changes to "hot reload" in a Flutter IDE.
21      // Notice that the counter didn't reset back to zero; the application
22      // is not restarted.
23      primarySwatch: Colors.blue,
24    );
25    // Home: MyHomePage(title: 'Flutter Demo Home Page')
26  }; // MaterialApp
27
28 }
29
30 class MyHomePage extends StatefulWidget {
31   // Home: MyHomePage(title: 'Flutter Demo Home Page')
32   MyHomePage({Key key, this.title}) : super(key: key);
33   // Home: MyHomePage(title: 'Flutter Demo Home Page')
```

Why Supabase?

Supabase was chosen for its robust online database storage and synchronization capabilities, ensuring seamless data management across devices and users.

Database Implementation

A relational database design, Supabase for online storage, and PostgreSQL for local storage form the backbone. Integration of Windows UI scheme ensures visual consistency and user familiarity.

WHAT PROBLEM DOES THIS PRODUCT FIX?

What is its magic?

How we'll measure success

This is what we bring to the table

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- | | |
|------------------------------------|----------------------------------|
| ✦ Secure user roles & permissions. | ✦ Customizable report generation |
| ✦ Intuitive Fluent UI design. | ✦ Integration with EHR & billing |
| ✦ Patient & Medicine management | ✦ Real-time data sync |
| ✦ Dynamic appointment scheduling | ✦ Performance Optimization |
| ✦ Automated reminders | ✦ Enhanced Security Measures |
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Why Fluent UI

Fluent UI was selected for its familiarity to Windows users, ensuring ease of navigation and usability across the application.

Comprehensive testing, including unit testing, integration testing, and system validation, ensures reliability and performance. From automated unit tests to user acceptance testing, each phase verifies functionality and usability.

Product summary

WHAT IS IN THE FUTURE?

Potential enhancements include server database setup, user training, and performance optimization, prioritizing continuous improvement and community engagement.

Free

Use the product Locally.
Enjoy 2Gb of cloud syncing

Enterprise

Custom Scaling based on
Infrastructure.
Cloud backup and Storage based
on pricing.

Sattra achieves milestones in database design, UI integration, and testing. While facing knowledge imbalances and time constraints, it sets the stage for future enhancements like server setup and user training, promising continued improvement in healthcare management

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THE END